

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of DL-methionine by thallium(III) in perchloric acid medium

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In continuation of our investigations on the oxidation of DL-methionine (Met), one of the sulfur containing optically active essential amino acids, using oxidants like manganese(III)¹, iron(III)-2,2'-bipyridyl² and bromate³, we now report the kinetics and mechanism of its oxidation using thallium(III) in aqueous perchloric acid medium. It is interesting to note that the protonated form of methionine is the reactive species in the manganese(III)¹ and bromate³ oxidations, the zwitterionic form is the active species in the oxidation by iron(III)-2,2'-bipyridyl².

Results and Discussion

Known amounts of methionine was allowed to react completely with 2-4 fold excess of Tl^{III} at 25° in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid medium and the unreacted Tl^{III} was estimated iodometrically. The stoichiometry was found to correspond to the equation,

A 0.4 mol dm⁻³ sodium bicarbonate solution was added to the reaction mixture (after completion of the reaction) with vigorous stirring followed by addition of benzoyl chloride solution until precipitation was completed. The precipitate obtained was confirmed to be *N*-benzoyl-methionine sulfoxide (a derivative of methionine sulfoxide), identified by its melting point⁴. Thallium(I), one of the reaction products was found to have no effect on the reaction rate.

The effect of ionic strength on the rate of reaction was studied by varying it from 0.5–1.5 mol dm⁻³ using lithium perchlorate, keeping the concentrations of all other species in the reaction mixture constant. The results (Table 1) show that the rate increases with the increase in ionic strength of the medium.

The initial rates were found to increase with increasing concentration of thallium(III) and methionine with unit

order dependence in each. The orders with respect to thallium(III) and methionine were also determined adopting isolation method in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid medium at 30°, where the reaction is relatively slow. The rate constants obtained at different concentrations of methionine and thallium(III) are recorded in Table 2. The second order rate constants (k_{obs}) computed from the pseudo-first order rate constants (k^1) confirm the order with respect to methionine and thallium(III) to be unity each. Other investigations could not be carried out employing isolation method because the reaction is considerably fast at higher acid concentrations, whereas at lower acid concentrations thallium(III) undergoes extensive hydrolysis.

Table 1. Effect of ionic strength on the initial rate of reaction
[Met] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Tl^{III}] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³,
[H⁺] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 25 ± 0.1°

μ mol dm ⁻³	Initial rate × 10 ⁶ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹
0.5	8.3
0.7	9.0
0.8	10.7
1.0	11.6
1.2	13.6
1.5	16.0

Table 2. Effect of [methionine] and [thallium(III)] on the rate constants
[H⁺] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 30 ± 0.1°

[Tl ^{III}] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[Met] × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	k^1 × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹	k_{obs} × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹
0.5	1.0	9.6	9.6
1.0	1.0	9.4	9.4
1.5	1.0	8.8	8.8
2.0	1.0	9.4	9.4
2.5	1.0	9.6	9.6
3.0	1.0	8.8	8.8
1.0	1.5	12.8	8.5
1.0	2.0	18.8	9.0
1.0	2.5	21.2	8.5
1.0	3.0	26.0	8.7

In order to study the effect of $[H^+]$ on the initial rate of reaction, kinetic runs were carried out at various perchloric acid concentrations over the 0.1–0.8 mol dm⁻³ range, keeping the ionic strength constant at 1.0 mol dm⁻³ using lithium perchlorate. The data (Table 3) indicate that the rate of reaction initially increases with increase in the $[H^+]$ and finally approaches to a limiting value at higher hydrogen ion concentrations. The effect of $[Cl^-]$ on the initial rate of reaction was studied by keeping the concentrations of all other species constant and varying the $[Cl^-]$ in the range $(1.0-70.0) \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³ using sodium chloride. The rate of the reaction was found to decrease with the increase in $[Cl^-]$ (Table 3) may be attributed to medium effect.

Table 3. Effect of $[H^+]$ and $[Cl^-]$ on the initial rate of reaction
 $[Met] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³, $[Tl^{III}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³,
 $\mu = 1.0$ mol dm⁻³, Temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

$[H^+]$ mol dm ⁻³	$[Cl^-]$ $\times 10^4$ mol dm ⁻³	Initial rate $\times 10^6$ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹
0.1	–	4.0
0.2	–	6.2
0.3	–	8.3
0.4	–	10.2
0.5	–	11.7
0.6	–	12.0
0.8	–	12.7
0.5	1.0	6.3
0.5	10.0	4.5
0.5	20.0	3.5
0.5	50.0	2.7
0.5	70.0	2.3

The effect of temperature on the initial rate of reaction was studied at 15, 20, 25 and 30° and the initial rate ($\times 10^6$, mol dm⁻³ s⁻¹) values were found to be 3.30, 5.0, 8.1 and 11.7, respectively. E_a and ΔS^\ddagger were calculated using least-squares method and found to be 61.7 ± 2.2 kJ mol⁻¹ and -28.8 ± 7.4 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, respectively.

The hydrolysis constant of thallium(III) at 25° reported by Biedermann⁵ is 0.073 mol dm⁻³ at $\mu = 3.0$ mol dm⁻³, whereas Rogers and Wained⁶ reported the value to be 0.086 mol dm⁻³ at $\mu = 1.5$ mol dm⁻³. Hence, under the present experimental conditions (0.1–0.8 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄) thallium(III) exists mostly as Tl^{3+} and partly in the form of $TlOH^{2+}$.

Under the present experimental conditions (0.5 mol dm⁻³ HClO₄) methionine also exists in the form of the protonated species, $CH_3SCH_2CH_2CH(NH_3^+)COOH$ (HR-S-CH₃) to an extent of 99%. In view of the conversion of

neutral species of methionine to its protonated form at higher hydrogen ion concentrations, only the latter may be considered to be the reactive species. Basing on these observations the mechanism proposed is presented in Scheme 1.

where, R = $-CH_2CH_2CH(NH_3^+)COO^-$. This mechanism leads to the rate law,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[Tl^{III}]}{dt} = k_1 [Tl^{3+}]_e [HR-S-CH_3] + k_2 [TlOH^{2+}]_e [HR-S-CH_3] \quad (4)$$

$$\text{But } [Tl^{3+}]_t = [Tl^{3+}]_e + [TlOH^{2+}]_e \quad (5)$$

$$\text{and } K_h = \frac{[TlOH^{2+}]_e [H^+]}{[Tl^{3+}]_e} \quad (6)$$

Substituting for $[Tl^{3+}]_e$ and $[TlOH^{2+}]_e$ from eqs. (5) and (6) in eq. (4), we get

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{\{k_1 [H^+] + k_2 K_h\}}{K_h + [H^+]} [Tl^{III}] [HR-S-CH_3] \quad (7)$$

The rate equation explains the observed first order with respect to Tl^{III} and methionine. It does not predict any clear cut dependence of rate on $[H^+]$. But experimental results show that the rate first increases with the increase in $[H^+]$ and finally attains a limiting value. This observation can be explained on the ground that at lower $[H^+]$ (0.1–0.5 mol dm⁻³), the term $k_2 K_h$ in the numerator and K_h in the denominator cannot be ignored in comparison with the terms $k_1 [H^+]$ and $[H^+]$, respectively. But at higher $[H^+]$ (0.8 mol dm⁻³ and above) the terms become negligible thereby resulting in a limiting rate. Thus at higher $[H^+]$, the rate equation reduces to the form,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[Tl^{III}]}{dt} = k_1 [Tl^{III}] [Met] \quad (8)$$

Eqn. (8) implies that as $[H^+]$ is increased $TlOH^{2+}$, progressively gets converted to Tl^{3+} and the contribution of the former species to the rate of the reaction becomes negligible.

Methionine is a sulfur containing amino acid having three coordinating centres, oxygen, nitrogen and sulfur⁷. The oxidation product of methionine depends on the nature of the oxidant. With oxidants such as iodine⁸, chloroauric acid⁹, chromium(VI)^{4,7}, cerium(IV)¹⁰, vanadium(V)¹⁰, hexacyanoferrate(III)^{11,12}, *N*-bromoacetamide¹³, *N*-chloro-

acetamide¹⁴, hexachloroiridate¹⁵, iron(III)-2,2'-bipyridyl² and bromate³, it is oxidized to the sulfoxide stage only, whereas with certain other oxidants like chloramine-B¹⁶, bromamine-B¹⁷, chloramine-T¹⁸ and manganese(III)¹ it is oxidized to the sulfone stage. In all these oxidations, electrophilic attack is reported to take place at the sulfur site. In the present investigation, the protonated form of methionine is considered to be the reactive species and the oxidant species being Tl³⁺. The intimate mechanism of this reaction may be represented as follows :

where R = -CH₂CH₂CH(NH₃⁺)COO⁻

Experimental

The strength of DL-methionine (Himedia) was determined by iodometric method¹⁹. Stock solution of thallium(III) perchlorate was prepared by taking thallium(I) solution on oxidation with excess of bromine water in presence of hydrochloric acid²⁰. The excess bromine was boiled off, cooled to room temperature and Tl precipitated as thallium(III) hydroxide using dilute ammonium hydroxide solution. It was then washed free from halides. Thallium(III) hydroxide thus prepared was dissolved in appropriate quantity of HClO₄ of known concentration. The strength of the solution was determined by iodometric method²⁰. Thallium(I) perchlorate was prepared by dissolving thallos carbonate (A.R., B.D.H.) in suitable quantity of perchloric acid and standardized bromatometrically²⁰.

The kinetics of the reaction were studied at 25° in 0.5 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid medium. Since the reaction between Tl^{III} and methionine was observed to be very fast even at 25°, rate measurements were made employing

equivalent concentrations of methionine and Tl^{III}. The reaction mixture was quenched by transferring aliquot at regular intervals of time into 2 mol dm⁻³ hydrochloric acid. The concentration of unreacted Tl^{III} was estimated by iodometric method. The initial rates were determined from the plots of [Tl^{III}] vs time, employing the mirror technique and the rates thus obtained were reproducible within ±8%.

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